

Artificial intelligence in colorectal surgery multidisciplinary team approach—From innovation to application

Author: Ali Murtada¹

Co-authors: Fatima Kayali², Matti Jubouri³, Samuel N. S. Ghattas¹, Samuel S. S. Rezk¹

Coordinators: Feroze Ahmed Mir¹, Ian Williamst, Mohamad Bashiru, Damian

Affiliations:

¹ Department of General Surgery, Ysbyty Glan Clwyd, Rhyl, UK

² University Hospitals Sussex, Worthing, West Sussex, UK

³ Hull York Medical School, University of York, York, UK

t Department of Vascular Surgery, University Hospital of Wales, Cardiff, UK

*u*Neurovascular Research Laboratory, Faculty of Life Sciences and Education, University of South Wales, Pontypool, UK

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has played a novel role in aiding healthcare system functions and enhancing the patient experience. Multidisciplinary teams (MDT) have become an integral part of disease and management planning, especially with the rising number of our aging population and the paucity of sufficient resources. The incorporation of MDTs facilitates a holistic approach to patient care, encompassing the physical, psychological, and social needs of patients and their families. Particularly with the growing number of colorectal cancer diagnoses, notably among the younger populations, the utilization of AI in the colorectal MDT holds great potential value.

Materials and methods

This narrative review article explores the role of AI in the colorectal surgery MDT, its drawbacks, and its merits.

Results

Multi- Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) or Multi- Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is an accurate decision-making method (Diaby et al., 2013). MCDM has the potential to minimize conflicts inherent in clinical decision-making, enhance knowledge, and achieve outcomes that reflect the values of the decision-makers. While there is no uniformly superior approach or method for applying MCDA, the decision-making context can guide the selection of the most appropriate method. When combined with AI techniques, MCDM provides powerful tools for making complex decisions in multifaceted situations. These methods aim to rank or prioritize alternatives by aggregating criteria and providing decision-makers with valuable insights. However, limitations on radiomics have been reported. To this effect, MCDM is both an approach and a set of techniques developed in decision theory to aid in problem solving.

Conclusion

Embracing AI to optimize decision-making within MDT reflects a commitment to adopting innovation and application. This approach can objectively provide reliable and comprehensive reference opinions, facilitating more accurate clinical decisions.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence, Colorectal Surgery, Multidisciplinary team